

Facile synthesis and biological evaluation of some ethoxyphthalimide derivatives of pyrazolylthiazoloisoxazoles and pyrazolylthiadiazoles

Bhawana Thadhaney, Shweta Sharma, Chirag Sharma and G. L. Talesara*

Synthetic Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University,
Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : gtalesara@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 15 December 2008, revised 15 May 2009, accepted 26 June 2009

Abstract : Reaction of acetylacetone with hydrazine hydrate gave 3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazole (1) which when reacted with ethylchloroacetate in acetone and thiosemicarbazide yielded ethyl-3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl-acetate (2) and 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)acetyl]hydrazine carbothioamide (3) respectively. Compound 3 acted as a key intermediate for both the series of final compounds. In one pathway, it was converted to corresponding thiadiazole (11) by treatment with conc. H₂SO₄ and NH₃ which on condensation with ω-bromoethoxyphthalimide (10) gave 5-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl]-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine (12). In another pathway, 3 reacted with chloroacetic acid to furnish 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazolyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]acetohydrazide (4). Reaction of 4 with various araldehydes (5a-d) gave 5-[(4-substituted phenyl)methylidene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (6a-d) which were further treated in two alternate routes. Firstly, with 10 to yield 5-[(4-substituted phenyl)methylidene]-3-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (8a-d). Cyclisation of these derivatives using hydroxylamine hydrochloride produced the target compounds 3-(4-substituted phenyl)-6-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*c*]isoxazol-5(6*H*)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (9a-d). In parallel, 6a-d were first cyclised with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to give 3-[(4-substituted phenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*c*]isoxazol-5(6*H*)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (7a-d) and then condensed with 10 to yield the final compounds 9a-d. Structural elucidation of synthesized compounds was accomplished by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data. Final compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Pyrazole, thiazole, isoxazole, thiadiazole, carbothioamide, ω-bromoethoxyphthalimide, thiazolidinone, thiosemicarbazide.

Introduction

Azoles have played a crucial part in the history of heterocyclic chemistry and also been used extensively as important synthons in organic synthesis. Owing to the versatile chemotherapeutical activities of azoles, a significant amount of research has been directed to this class. Thiadiazole is a versatile pharmacophore possessing a wide variety of biological activities, few of them are worth mentioning such as diuretic¹, antiviral, antihypertensive², insecticidal³, antimicrobial⁴ and many more. The interesting pharmacological properties of thiazole derivatives⁵ in relation to the various changes in the structures of these compounds is worth studying in order to synthesize less toxic and more potent drugs. Therefore the fusion of other heterocyclic moieties to the thiazole ring may lead to the fulfillment of the objective. A survey of literature

reveals that a number of 2,4-disubstituted 1,3-thiazoles were reported to exhibit antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antitumor and cytotoxic activities^{6,7}. 2-Substituted-thiazolidin-4-one derivatives exhibit unusual high activity *in vitro* against Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (TB), as drugs for anti-HIV and anti-cancer activity^{8,9}. Furthermore, 4-thiazolidinones have been synthesized¹⁰ and used for the treatment of cardiac¹¹ diseases. Pyrazoline derivatives have been studied extensively because of their ready accessibility, diverse chemical reactivity and broad biological activity. The pharmaceutical importance of variously substituted pyrazolines lies in the fact that they possess antibacterial, antifungal¹², anti-inflammatory¹³ and analgesic¹⁴, antiamebic¹⁵ and antidepressant¹⁶ properties. Isoxazoles, another class of azoles possess antiviral, antimicrobial¹⁷,

antiepileptic^{18,19} properties. Substituted isoxazole carbaldehydes²⁰ are discovered as spermicides, acrosin inhibitors and mild antifungal agents. A large number of imidoxy derivatives of various heterocycles reported to demonstrate a wide range of pharmacological activities like antimalarial²¹, anticonvulsant²², anticancer²³ etc. Several derivatives of this framework have been synthesized²⁴⁻²⁷ by our group of workers. In view of above mentioned facts and in continuation of our ongoing work, it appeared expedient to synthesize 3-(4-substituted phenyl)-6-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3*a*-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-*c*]isoxazol-5(6*H*)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (**9a-d**) and 5-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine (**12**).

Results and discussion

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to synthesise ethoxyphthalimide derivatives of some pyrazolylthiazoloisoxazoles and pyrazolylthiadiazoles

through a multistep process. For this purpose, the required 3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazole (**1**) was prepared by cyclisation reaction between acetylacetone and hydrazine hydrate. Reaction of **1** with ethylchloroacetate in acetone, yielded ethyl-3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl-acetate (**2**) which when condensed with thiosemicarbazide gave 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)acetyl]hydrazine carbothioamide (**3**). Formation of **3** was confirmed by the presence of N-H stretching peaks at 3376 and 3239 cm⁻¹ in IR and a multiplet at δ 8.4 for NH.NH.C=S.NH₂ group in ¹H NMR spectra. Treatment of **3** with conc. H₂SO₄ followed by NH₃ furnished 5-[(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine (**11**). Structure of **11** was confirmed on the basis of C-S-C linkage in the thiadiazole ring, which caused a sharp absorption band at 616 cm⁻¹ in its IR spectrum and ¹H NMR showed a fine singlet at δ 4.7 due to NH₂ functionality. Compound **11** was converted to corresponding ethoxyphthalimide derivative (**12**) by its reaction with ω -

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds **7a-d**, **9a-d** and **12**

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm) (activity index) ^{std}				Antifungal activity	
	Antibacterial activity					
	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aureoginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>
7a	12 (0.70)	13 (0.81)	10 (0.62)	12 (0.66)	13 (0.76)	9 (0.9)
7b	9 (0.53)	11 (0.68)	8 (0.5)	10 (0.55)	15 (0.88)	8 (0.8)
7c	8 (0.47)	9 (0.56)	7 (0.43)	9 (0.50)	12 (0.71)	7 (0.7)
7d	10 (0.59)	11 (0.68)	9 (0.56)	11 (0.61)	11 (0.64)	9 (0.9)
9a	14 (0.82)	15 (0.93)	11 (0.68)	17 (0.94)	20 (1.18)	14 (1.4)
9b	11 (0.64)	12 (0.75)	10 (0.62)	13 (0.72)	19 (1.12)	13 (1.3)
9c	10 (0.59)	9 (0.56)	9 (0.56)	10 (0.55)	15 (0.88)	10 (1.0)
9d	9 (0.53)	7 (0.44)	11 (0.68)	12 (0.66)	14 (0.82)	11 (1.1)
12	12 (0.70)	14 (0.87)	10 (0.62)	11 (0.61)	21 (1.23)	13 (1.3)
C ₁	17	16	16	18	17	10

(Activity index) = Inhibition zone of compound/Inhibition zone of the standard drug.

For antibacterial activity : C₁ = Ciprofloxacin.

For antifungal activity : C₁ = Amphotericin B.

Reaction Scheme

bromoethoxyphthalimide (10). IR and ¹H NMR spectra revealed carbonyl absorption band at 1726 cm⁻¹ for CO-N-CO group, N-O stretching band at 1356 cm⁻¹ and two triplets respectively at δ 3.02 and 2.78 for OCH₂ and NCH₂ group of ethoxyphthalimide moiety in 12. In another pathway, 3 was reacted with chloroacetic acid in presence of sodium acetate to afford 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene] acetohy-

drazide (4). IR and ¹H NMR spectrum of 4 showed bands at 1742, 1698 cm⁻¹ due to carbonyl stretching and signals at δ 5.6 (singlet), 4.4 (singlet) due to thiazolidinone ring respectively. Reaction of 4 with araldehydes (5a-d) gave 5-[(4-substituted phenyl)methylene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)-acetohydrazide (6a-d). The assigned structure of 6a-d was based on the obtained analytical and spectral data.

Reaction Scheme

Subsequently, N-H proton in the thiazolidinone ring was replaced by ethoxyphthalimide group upon its reaction with **10** to yield 5-[(4-substituted phenyl)methylidene]-3-*N*-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1*H*-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (**8a-d**). Presence of C-O and N-O stretching bands at 1025 and 1368 cm⁻¹ respectively in IR spectrum and δ 2.17 (2H, t, NCH₂), 2.72 (2H, t, OCH₂), in ¹H NMR spectrum for

ethyl side chain protons corroborated the structure of **8b**. Cyclisation of **8a-d** with hydroxylamine hydrochloride furnished the final compounds **9a-d**. Disappearance of ¹H NMR signal for CH proton of C=CH-Ar unit of thiazolidinone moiety in NMR spectra of **9a-d** confirmed the formation of target compounds. Mass spectra and ¹³C NMR spectra also supported the proposed structures of synthesized compounds.

Antimicrobial screening :

Antimicrobial activity i.e. antibacterial and antifungal was screened by Well or Cup method²⁹ in nutrient agar and dextrose agar medium. Agar medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 psi and 121 °C for twenty minutes. The medium was poured in Petri dishes and left to solidify. These Petri dishes were inoculated with 0.2 mL suspension of organism by spread plate method³⁰. Three or four wells of 11 mm diameter were made in the medium with the help of a sterile borer and filled with 500 ppm solution of testing compound in DMF. Similarly other wells were made for standard drugs and filled with standard concentration. These Petri plates were incubated at 37 °C in an incubator. The Petri dishes were examined for zone of inhibition after 48 h. Bacterial strains used for the present investigation are *P. aureoginosa*, *P. mirabilis*, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. Ciprofloxacin was used as a standard drug. *Candida albicans* (MTCC227) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* (MTCC2550) were used as the testing fungal strains and Amphotericin B was used as standard drug. Zone of inhibition is measured in mm. Activity index of all the synthesized compounds was also calculated against all the standard drugs.

Nine compounds viz. **12**, **9a-d** and **7a-d** were assayed for antimicrobial activity. Screening results of the compounds **9a-d** established that **9a** showed comparable activity against all the tested micro-organisms as compared to the standard drugs used, while **9b** exhibited good activity and **9c** and **9d** displayed moderate activity against all the four bacterial and two fungal strains. Overall activity profile of compounds **7a-d** was found to be good.

Therefore in the present study, we attempted to increase antimicrobial activities by fusing ethoxyphthalimide moiety with thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazole ring system. As a result, all the final compounds displayed promising activity against pathogenic microbes. Compound **9a** was found to be the strongest amongst all. Compounds have more comprehensive fungus-inhibiting properties than that of the bacterial. Compound **9a** and **9b** showed strong activity against *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aureoginosa*, *C. albicans* and *A. fumigatus* while moderate to good activity against *P. mirabilis* and *E. coli*. The effect of incorporation of ethoxyphthalimide moiety to the thiazole ring system was much pronounced on their activity. As far as the relation between structure and activity are concerned the chloro and methoxy substituted compounds were found to display enhanced activity than the other substituents.

Experimental

General procedures : Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are therefore uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel G TLC plates of 2 mm thickness using *n*-hexane and ethylacetate as solvent system. The visualization of spot was carried out in an iodine chamber. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded in the 4000–450 cm⁻¹ ranges using KBr discs on Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometers and ¹H NMR were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 MHz spectrometer (CDCl₃) using TMS as an internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AC (75.47 MHz) in DMSO. Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-600 mass spectrometer. Phthalimidoxyethyl bromide²⁸ (**10**) was synthesized by literature method.

Synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (1) :

A mixture of acetylacetone (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 mol) was stirred for an hour in a conical flask on an ice bath and resultant solid was separated, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. (**1**) : Yield 74%, m.p. 102 °C (Found : N, 29.12. Calcd. for C₃H₈N₂ : N, 29.14%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3420 (N–H str.), 1630 (C=N str.), 2970 (C–H str., CH₃), 1225 (C–N str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 2.1 (6H, s, CH₃), 8.3 (1H, s, NH), 3.2 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 14.2 (CH₃), 52.1 (=C–CH₃), 99.8 (C=CH).

Synthesis of ethyl-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl-acetate (2) :

To a solution of 3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (**1**) (0.01 mol) in acetone, ethylchloroacetate (0.01 mol) was added dropwise and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.02 mol) was used as a base. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 7 h and filtered hot. Solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to concentrate the product as white shining crystals on cooling. Recrystallization was carried out from ethanol. (**2**) : Yield 70%, m.p. 89 °C (Found : N, 15.31. Calcd. for C₉H₁₄N₂O₂ : N, 15.37%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 2974 (C–H str., CH₃), 2934 (C–H str., CH₂), 1744 (C=O str.), 1634 (C=N str.), 1221 (C–N str.), 1027 (C–O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 2.3 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (1H, s, CH), 4.26 (2H, q, COOCH₂CH₃), 3.68 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.28 (3H, t, COOCH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR δ : 15.7 (CH₃), 54.6 (=C–CH₃), 103.1 (C=CH), 49.2 (CH₂CO), 153 (CH₂CO), 68.4 (OCH₂CH₃).

Synthesis of 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetyl]hydrazine carbothioamide (3) :

An equimolar mixture of **2** (0.01 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 8–10 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and the obtained yellow solid was recrystallised from alcohol. (**3**) : Yield 67%, m.p. 130 °C (Found : N, 30.85; S, 14.05. Calcd. for C₈H₁₃N₅OS : N, 30.81; S, 14.11 %).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3376, 3239 (N–H str.), 2968 (C–H str., CH₃), 2938 (CH str., CH₂), 1738 (C=O str.), 1629 (C=N str.), 1105 (C=S str.), 1218 (C–N str.); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.1 (CH₃), 51.6 (=C–CH₃), 107.5 (C=CH), 44.2 (CH₂CO), 155 (CH₂CO), 154 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 2.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.7 (1H, s, CH), 8.4 (4H, m, NH.NH.C=S.NH₂), 3.64 (2H, s, NCH₂).

Synthesis of 2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene acetohydrazide (4) :

Carbothioamide **3** (0.01 mol) and chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) were dissolved in absolute alcohol, anhydrous sodium acetate (0.02 mol) was added to it as a base. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 10 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and then the residual concentrated solution was poured on crushed ice. Precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised from absolute ethanol. (**4**) : Yield 72%, m.p. 142 °C (Found : N, 26.18; S, 11.6 Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃N₅O₂S : N, 26.20; S, 12.00 %).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 2976 (C–H str., CH₃), 2853 (C–H str., CH₂), 3340, 3412 (N–H str.), 3125 (C–H str., Ar–H), 1742, 1698 (C=O str.), 1627 (C=N str.), 1219 (C–N str.), 680 (C–S–C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.10 (1H, s, CONH), 5.6 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 4.4 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.6 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.2 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.8 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 17.4 (CH₃), 54.6 (=C–CH₃), 105.3 (C=CH), 48.1 (CH₂CO), 161 (CH₂CO), 168 (SCN), 177 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 31.2 (CH₂ of thiazolidinone).

Synthesis of 5-[(4-chlorophenyl)methylidene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (6a) :

To a refluxing mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.02 mol) as a base in gl. acetic acid, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde **5a** (0.01 mol) was added and refluxing continued for 16 h. After completion of reaction, icecold water was added to the reaction mixture. Yellow

coloured solid was filtered, washed and crystallized from ethanol. (**6a**) : Yield 65%, m.p. 184 °C (Found : N, 17.93; S, 8.24. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆ClN₅O₂S : N, 17.96; S, 8.22 %).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3400, 3419 (N–H str.), 3058 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2866 (C–H str., CH₂), 1735, 1660 (C=O str.), 756 (C–Cl str.), 678 (C–S–C str.), 1620 (C=N str.), 1217 (C–N str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.31 (1H, s, CONH), 6.96–7.44 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.2 (1H, s, C=CH–Ar), 5.5 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.2 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.9 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 18.6 (CH₃), 58.3 (=C–CH₃), 108.2 (C=CH), 44.2 (CH₂CO), 160 (CH₂CO), 165 (SCN), 172 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 115 (C–C=O), 126.9–134.3 (aromatic carbons).

Similarly, other compounds **6b–d** were also synthesized and their characteristic spectral data are given below :

5-[(4-Methoxy phenyl)methylidene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (6b) :

Yield 62%, m.p. 199 °C (Found : N, 18.20; S, 8.31. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₉N₅O₃S : N, 18.17; S, 8.32 %).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3392, 3407 (N–H str.), 3021 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2843 (C–H str., CH₂), 1722, 1603 (C=O str.), 2950 (C–H str., CH₃), 1610 (C=N str.), 628 (C–S–C str.), 1233 (C–N str.), 1029 (C–O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.47 (1H, s, CONH), 7.0–7.6 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.5 (1H, s, C=CH–Ar), 5.7 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.38 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.49 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.1 (CH₃), 54.4 (=C–CH₃), 102.2 (C=CH), 41.2 (CH₂CO), 151 (CH₂CO), 169 (SCN), 164 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 112 (C–C=O), 121.5–130.0 (aromatic carbons), 124.9 (C–OCH₃), 54.73 (OCH₃),

5-[(4-Dimethylamino phenyl)methylidene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (6c) :

Yield 66%, m.p. 206 °C (Found : N, 21.05; S, 8.11. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₂N₆O₂S : N, 21.09; S, 8.05 %).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3364, 3401 (N–H str.), 3014 (C–H str., Ar–H), 2851 (C–H str., CH₂), 1716, 1600 (C=O str.), 2938 (C–H str., CH₃), 1602 (C=N str.), 614 (C–S–C str.), 1202 (C–N str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.40 (1H, s, CONH), 7.14–7.65 (4H, m, Ar–H), 6.7 (1H, s, C=CH–Ar), 5.9 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 2.35 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.40 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.52 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 15.1 (CH₃), 51.2 (=C–CH), 107.2

(C=CH), 41.3 (CH₂CO), 153 (CH₂CO), 162 (SCN), 166 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 115 (C-C=O), 128.4–130.7 (aromatic carbons).

5-[(4-Phenyl)methylidene]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene]-2-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (6d) :

Yield 73%, m.p. 179 °C (Found : N, 19.68; S, 9.05. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₇N₅O₂S : N, 19.70; S, 9.02%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3398, 3404 (N-H str.), 3044 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2849 (C-H str., CH₂) 1728, 1635 (C=O str.), 2954 (C-H str., CH₃), 1614 (C=N str.), 655 (C-S-C str.), 1212 (C-N str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.28 (1H, s, CONH), 7.00–7.48 (5H, m, Ar-H), 6.4 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 5.6 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.31 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.41 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR δ : 17.3 (CH₃), 54.3 (=C-CH₃), 106.2 (C=CH), 44.3 (CH₂CO), 153 (CH₂CO), 165.3 (SCN), 161 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 112 (C-C=O), 120.1–131.5 (aromatic carbons).

Synthesis of 3-(4-chloro phenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]-thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (7a) :

To a solution of compound 6a (0.01 mol) in acetic acid, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in absolute alcohol and sodium acetate were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 7–8 h. The filtrate was slowly poured into ice (50 g) with constant stirring. Solid obtained was recrystallized from ethanol. (7a) : Yield 62%, m.p. 231 °C (Found : N, 20.71; S, 7.90. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₇ClN₆O₂S : N, 20.76; S, 7.92%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3379, 3413 (N-H str.), 3061 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2861 (C-H str., CH₂), 1738 (C=O str.), 2953 (C-H str., CH₃), 1248 (C-N str.), 679 (C-S-C str.), 1375 (N-O str.), 1597 (C=N str.), 1087 (C-O str.), 702 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.21 (1H, s, CONH), 7.38–7.79 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.4 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.31 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.51 (1H, s, CH), 4.23 (1H, d, CHO); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.4 (CH₃), 53.8 (=C-CH₃), 99.6 (C=CH), 44.7 (CH₂CO), 171 (C=O), 164 (C=N), 124.4–137.2 (aromatic CH), 130.9 (C-Cl).

Compounds 7b–d were prepared in similar ways with minor changes in reflux time. Their spectral data are given below :

3-(4-Methoxy phenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (7b) :

Yield 57%, m.p. 223 °C (Found : N, 20.96; S, 7.94. Calcd. for C₁₈H₂₀N₆O₃S : N, 20.99; S, 8.01%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3394, 3407 (N-H str.), 3059 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2869 (C-H str., CH₂), 1731 (C=O str.), 2972 (C-H str., CH₃), 1241 (C-N str.), 677 (C-S-C str.), 1371 (N-O str.), 1612 (C=N str.), 1091 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.17 (1H, s, CONH), 7.45–7.89 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.7 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.28 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.44 (1H, s, CH), 4.28 (1H, d, CHO), 3.63 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.2 (CH₃), 51.1 (=C-CH₃), 106.4 (C=CH), 49.1 (CH₂), 163 (C=O), 170 (C=N), 120.9–136.4 (aromatic CH), 130.7 (C-OCH₃), 51.60 (OCH₃).

3-(4-Dimethylamino phenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (7c) :

Yield 62%, m.p. 244 °C (Found : N, 23.76; S, 7.71. Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₃N₇O₂S : N, 23.71; S, 7.75%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3381, 3399 (N-H str.), 3051 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2887 (C-H str., CH₂), 1728 (C=O str.), 2962 (C-H str., CH₃), 1206 (C-N str.), 671 (C-S-C str.), 1364 (N-O str.), 1598 (C=N str.), 1089 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.12 (1H, s, CONH), 7.21–7.63 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.6 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.21 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.36 (1H, s, CH), 4.23 (1H, d, CHO), 2.62 (6H, s, NMe₂); ¹³C NMR δ : 13.7 (CH₃), 53.7 (=C-CH₃), 106.7 (C=CH), 42.9 (CH₂), 163.5 (C=O), 169 (C=N), 120–135.8 (aromatic CH), 127.8 (C-NMe₂).

3-(4-Phenyl)-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (7d) :

Yield 71%, m.p. 239 °C (Found : N, 22.67; S, 8.65. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈N₆O₂S : N, 22.69; S, 8.66%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3391, 3404 (N-H str.), 3063 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2874 (C-H str., CH₂), 1746 (C=O str.), 2659 (C-H str., CH₃), 1233 (C-N str.), 664 (C-S-C str.), 1368 (N-O str.), 1607 (C=N str.), 1074 (C-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.14 (1H, s, CONH), 7.21–7.63 (5H, m, Ar-H), 5.2 (1H, s, NH of thiazolidinone ring), 3.29 (2H, s, NCH₂), 2.39 (1H, s, CH), 4.16 (1H, d, CHO); ¹³C NMR δ : 15.3 (CH₃), 51.8 (=C-CH₃), 100.7 (C=CH), 48.3 (CH₂), 168.1 (C=O), 161.4 (C=N), 127.3–134.8 (aromatic CH).

Synthesis of 5-[(4-chloro phenyl)methylidene]-3-N-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (8a) :

Compound **6a** (0.01 mol) and ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide (**10**) (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 30 mL DMF and then pyridine (2 mL) was added to it as a base. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 19 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. Resulting solid was cooled, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. Yield 67%, m.p. 246 °C (Found : N, 14.49; S, 5.49. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₃ClN₆O₅S : N, 14.51; S, 5.54%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3393 (N-H str.), 3034 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2881 (C-H str., CH₂), 2964 (C-H str., CH₃), 1611, 1692, 1729 (C=O str.), 1043 (C-O str.), 1632 (C=N str.), 1224 (C-N str.), 1346¹ (N-O str.), 675 (C-S-C str.), 743 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.39 (1H, s, CONH), 7.1-7.7 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.2 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 2.04 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.21 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 2.69 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.86 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 13.9 (CH₃), 52.4 (=C-CH₃), 104.2 (C=CH), 48.3 (CH₂CO), 159 (CH₂CO), 168 (SCN), 164.7 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 117.8 (C-C=O), 120.1-131.5 (aromatic carbons), 138.6 (C-Cl), 75.1 (OCH₂), 57.9 (NCH₂).

Compounds **8b-d** have been prepared by similar process. Their spectral data are given below :

Synthesis of 5-[(4-methoxy phenyl)methylidene]-3-N-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (8b) :

Yield 64%, m.p. 241 °C (Found : N, 14.59; S, 5.64. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₆N₆O₆S : N, 14.63; S, 5.58%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3379 (N-H str.), 3021 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2864 (C-H str., CH₂), 2958 (C-H str., CH₃), 1603, 1684, 1722 (C=O str.), 1025 (C-O str.), 1623 (C=N str.), 1215 (C-N str.), 1368 (N-O str.), 670 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.37 (1H, s, CONH), 7.0-7.67 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.7 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.11 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.17 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 2.72 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.80 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.5 (CH₃), 50.7 (=C-CH₃), 102.8 (C=CH), 49.6 (CH₂CO), 161.6 (CH₂CO), 164.3 (SCN), 169.6 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 116.2 (C-C=O), 125.5-138.2 (aromatic carbons), 159.9 (C-OCH₃), 73.4 (OCH₂), 54.7 (NCH₂).

Synthesis of 5-[(4-dimethylaminophenyl)methylidene]-3-N-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (8c) :

Yield 68%, m.p. 273 °C (Found : N, 16.65 : S, 5.41. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₉N₇O₅S : N, 16.68 : S, 5.46%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3376 (N-H str.), 3016 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2871 (C-H str., CH₂), 2946 (C-H str., CH₃), 1600, 1679, 1719 (C=O str.), 1012 (C-O str.), 1617 (C=N str.), 1209 (C-N str.), 1373 (N-O str.), 629 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.41 (1H, s, CONH), 7.4-7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.5 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 2.74 (6H, s, NMe₂), 2.04 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.21 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 2.68 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.84 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 11.8 (CH₃), 57.2 (=C-CH₃), 101.1 (C=CH), 47.6 (CH₂CO), 160.1 (CH₂CO), 167.9 (SCN), 173 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 112.2 (C-C=O), 128.0-134.9 (aromatic carbons), 70.1 (OCH₂), 51.7 (NCH₂).

Synthesis of 5-[(4-phenyl)methylidene]-3-N-ethoxyphthalimido-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene}-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolyl)acetohydrazide (8d) :

Yield 69%, m.p. 216 °C (Found : N, 15.47; S, 5.83. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄N₆O₅S : N, 15.43; S, 5.89%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3391 (N-H str.), 3028 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2894 (C-H str., CH₂), 2961 (C-H str., CH₃), 1609, 1698, 1727 (C=O str.), 1034 (C-O str.), 1631 (C=N str.), 1219 (C-N str.), 1394 (N-O str.), 681 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.29 (1H, s, CONH), 7.0-7.2 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.28 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 2.07 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.13 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 2.61 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.76 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 12.9 (CH₃), 59.4 (=C-CH₃), 108.1 (C=CH), 41.6 (CH₂CO), 162.8 (CH₂CO), 165.2 (SCN), 176 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 117.6 (C-C=O), 126.3-132.7 (aromatic carbons), 67.4 (OCH₂), 57.2 (NCH₂).

Synthesis of 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-N-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (9a) :

It was prepared by following two pathways : (i) Compound **7a** (0.01 mol) and ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide (**10**) (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 30 ML DMF and then pyridine (2 mL) was added to it as a base. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 22 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. Resulting solid was cooled, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. (ii) To a solution of compound **8a** (0.01 mol) in acetic acid, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in absolute alcohol and sodium acetate were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h. The filtrate was slowly poured into ice (50 g) with constant stirring. Solid obtained was recrystallized from ethanol. (**9a**) : Yield 66% m.p. 282 °C (Found : N, 16.45; S, 5.36. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₄ClN₇O₅S : N, 16.51; S, 5.40%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3386 (N-H str.), 3082 (C-H str.,

Ar-H), 2864 (C-H str., CH₂), 2941 (C-H str., CH₃), 1751, 1690 (C=O str.), 1078 (C-O str.), 1649 (C=N str.), 1222 (C-N str.), 1370 (N-O str.), 684 (C-S-C str.), 731 (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.26 (1H, s, CONH), 7.04–7.79 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.8 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.60 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 3.04 (2H, t, OCH₂), 3.79 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 17.8 (CH₃), 56.4 (=C-CH₃), 96.6 (C=CH), 47.7 (CH₂), 175 (C=O), 169 (C=N), 128.4 (aromatic CH), 132.1 (C-Cl), 70.7 (OCH₂), 55.4 (NCH₂); MS : *m/z* 596 [M+2]⁺, 594 [M]⁺, 483 [M-C₆H₄Cl]⁺, 454 [M-C₇H₅ClO]⁺, 415 [M-C₉H₆ClON]⁺, 273 [M-C₁₇H₁₀ClO₃N₂]⁺, 229 [M-C₁₉H₁₄ClO₄N₂]⁺, 171 [M-C₂₀H₁₄ClO₄N₃S]⁺, 157 [M-C₂₀H₁₄ClO₄N₄S]⁺, 142 [M-C₂₀H₁₅ClO₄N₅S]⁺, 114 [M-C₂₁H₁₅ClO₅N₅S]⁺, 100 [M-C₂₂H₁₇ClO₅N₅S]⁺, 72 [M-C₂₂H₁₇ClO₅N₇S]⁺.

Compounds **9b-d** have been prepared by similar process with minor changes in reaction conditions. Spectral data are given below :

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-6-N-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (9b) :

Yield 58%, m.p. 279 °C (Found : N, 16.50; S, 5.53. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₇N₇O₆S : N, 16.63; S, 5.44%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3382 (N-H str.), 3020 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2726 (C-H str., CH₂), 2959 (C-H str., CH₃), 1719, 1638 (C=O str.), 1038 (C-O str.), 1608 (C=N str.), 1217 (C-N str.), 1326 (N-O str.), 678 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.33 (1H, s, CONH), 7.45–7.89 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.11 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.67 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 3.214 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.69 (1H, s, CH), 3.31 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.9 (CH₃), 54.1 (=C-CH₃), 102.4 (C=CH), 42.1 (CH₂), 169 (C=O), 172 (C=N), 123.4 (aromatic CH), 132.1 (C-OCH₃), 55.20 (OCH₃), 68.4 (OCH₂), 53.2 (NCH₂); MS : *m/z* 590 [M]⁺, 559 [M-OCH₃]⁺, 534 [M-OC₃H₄]⁺, 483 [M-OC₇H₇]⁺, 440 [M-O₂C₈H₈N]⁺, 364 [M-O₂C₁₄H₁₂N]⁺, 294 [M-O₄C₁₆H₁₂N₂]⁺, 250 [M-O₅C₁₈H₁₆N₂]⁺, 179 [M-O₅C₂₀H₁₇N₃S]⁺, 138 [M-O₅C₂₁H₁₈N₅S]⁺, 96 [M-O₆C₂₃H₂₀N₅S]⁺.

3-(4-Dimethylaminophenyl)-6-N-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (9c) :

Yield 60%, m.p. 214 °C (Found : N, 18.63; S, 5.25. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₀N₈O₅S : N, 18.59; S, 5.32%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3374 (N-H str.), 3053 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2777 (C-H str., CH₂), 2964 (C-H str., CH₃), 1724, 1635 (C=O str.), 1029 (C-O str.), 1619 (C=N str.), 1228 (C-N str.), 1306 (N-O str.), 670 (C-S-C str.);

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.39 (1H, s, CONH), 7.49–7.78 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.38 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 2.14 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.71 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 3.106 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.68 (1H, s, CH), 3.37 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 15.1 (CH₃), 58.9 (=C-CH₃), 107.1 (C=CH), 49.6 (CH₂), 160 (C=O), 167 (C=N), 121.5 (aromatic CH), 130 (C-NMe₂), 70.2 (OCH₂), 51.4 (NCH₂); MS : *m/z* 603 [M]⁺, 559 [M-C₂H₆N]⁺, 483 [M-C₈H₁₀N]⁺, 440 [M-C₉H₁₁N₂O]⁺, 364 [M-C₁₅H₁₅N₂O]⁺, 294 [M-C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₃]⁺, 264 [M-C₁₈H₁₇N₃O₄]⁺, 211 [M-C₂₁H₂₀N₄O₄]⁺, 167 [M-C₂₂H₂₀N₄O₄S]⁺, 138 [M-C₂₂H₂₁N₆O₄S]⁺, 110 [M-C₂₃H₂₁N₆O₅S]⁺, 68 [M-C₂₄H₂₃N₈O₅S]⁺.

3-(4-Phenyl)-6-N-ethoxyphthalimido-3,3a-dihydro[1,3]thiazolo[4,5-c]isoxazol-5(6H)-ylidene-2-(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)acetohydrazide (9d) :

Yield 66%, m.p. 247 °C (Found : N, 17.48; S, 5.74. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₅N₇O₅S : N, 17.52; S, 5.73%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3379 (N-H str.), 3028 (C-H str., Ar-H), 2794 (C-H str., CH₂), 2978 (C-H str., CH₃), 1724, 1649 (C=O str.), 1048 (C-O str.), 1640 (C=N str.), 1201 (C-N str.), 1329 (N-O str.), 673 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 8.29 (1H, s, CONH), 7.38–7.94 (9H, m, Ar-H), 2.04 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.62 (2H, t, N-CH₂), 3.71 (2H, t, OCH₂), 2.54 (1H, s, CH), 3.42 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR δ : 16.2 (CH₃), 53.7 (=C-CH₃), 98.7 (C=CH), 44.6 (CH₂), 169 (C=O), 162 (C=N), 121.4 (aromatic CH), 76.1 (OCH₂), 56.8 (NCH₂); MS : *m/z* 560 [M]⁺, 483 [M-C₆H₅]⁺, 454 [M-C₇H₆O]⁺, 378 [M-C₁₃H₁₀O]⁺, 292 [M-C₁₅H₁₀NO₄]⁺, 264 [M-C₁₇H₁₄NO₄]⁺, 211 [M-C₁₉H₁₅N₃O₄]⁺, 167 [M-C₂₀H₁₅N₃O₄S]⁺, 153 [M-C₂₀H₁₅N₄O₄S]⁺, 110 [M-C₂₁H₁₆N₅O₅S]⁺, 96 [M-C₂₂H₁₈N₅O₅S]⁺, 82 [M-C₂₂H₁₈N₆O₅S]⁺.

Synthesis of 5-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine (11) :

Compound **3** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 4 mL conc. H₂SO₄. This solution was stirred at room temperature for few minutes and left overnight. It was then poured on crushed ice. The resulting suspension was kept in ammonical water for 2 h, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals. (**11**) : Yield 62%, m.p. 192 °C (Found : N, 35.84; S, 16.38. Calcd. for C₇H₉N₅S : N, 35.87; S, 16.42%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3350, 3268 (N-H str.), 2986 (C-H str., CH₃), 1626 (C=N str.), 1258 (C-N str.), 616 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 2.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.7 (2H, s, NH₂), 2.4 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C

NMR δ : 15.9 (CH₃), 51.8 (=C-CH₃), 109 (C=CH), 156 (C=N), 156.7, 160.7 (thiadiazole carbons).

Synthesis of 5-[(3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazol-1-yl)methyl]-N-ethoxyphthalimido-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine (12) :

Compound 11 (0.01 mol) was refluxed in dry acetone (20 mL) containing K₂CO₃ (0.02 mol) as base and ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide (10) (0.01 mol) for 15–17 h. Excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Resulting solid was cooled, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. (12) : Yield 59%, m.p. 253 °C (Found : N, 21.84; S, 8.31. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₆O₃S : N, 21.86; S, 8.34%).

IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3431 (N-H str.), 2841 (C-H str., CH₂), 3083 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1726 (C=O str.), 2916 (C-H str., CH₃), 1598 (C=N str.), 1356 (N-O str.), 1064 (C-O str.), 698 (C-S-C str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 7.76–7.82 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.28 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.78 (2H, t, NHCH₂), 2.95 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 3.02 (2H, t, OCH₂), 5.09 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR δ : 14.8 (CH₃), 53.4 (=C-CH₃), 103 (C=CH), 164 (C=O), 156 (C=N), 124.2 (aromatic CH), 73.6 (OCH₂), 52 (NCH₂), 152.1, 163.2 (thiadiazole carbons); MS : *m/z* 384 [M]⁺, 308 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 238 [M-C₈H₄O₂N]⁺, 179 [M-C₁₀H₉O₃N₂]⁺, 121 [M-C₁₁H₉O₃N₃S]⁺, 67 [M-C₁₂H₉O₃N₆S]⁺.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur, for providing Laboratory facilities and to the Director, RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow, for providing spectral and analytical data. Authors are grateful to Antimicrobial Research Laboratory, particularly Dr. Kanika Sharma, Department of Botany, M. L. Sukhadia University for evaluating antimicrobial activity.

References

1. S. K. Jain and A. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 184.
2. V. K. Pandey, T. Sarah and T. Zarah, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 180.
3. K. S. Rao, K. Shridhar and V. G. Bhatt, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 2170.
4. A. A. Aly and R. El-Sayed, *Chem. Pap.*, 2006, **60**, 56.
5. H. N. Liu, Z. C. Liu and T. Anthosen, *Molecules*, 2000, **5**, 1055.
6. R. Bai, A. Kepler, T. D. Copeland, N. Y. Nguyen, G. R. Pettit and E. Hamel, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2004, **30**, 731.
7. E. Brantley, V. Patel, S. F. Stinson, V. Trapani, C. D. Hose, H. P. Ciolino, G. C. Yeh, J. S. Gutkind, E. A. Sausville and A. I. Loaiza, *Anticancer Drugs*, 2005, **16**, 137.
8. K. Babaoglu, M. A. Page, V. C. Jones, M. R. McNeil, C. Dong, J. H. Naismith and R. E. Lee, *Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 3227.
9. A. Rao, J. Balzarini, A. Carbone, A. Chimirri, E. De Clercq, A. M. Monforte, P. Monforte, C. Pannecouque and M. Zappala, *Farmaco*, 2004, **59**, 33.
10. M. Amir, M. S. Y. Khan and M. S. Zaman, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 2189.
11. N. Hrib and J. Jurcak, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, **35**, 2712.
12. Z. G. Turan, A. Ozdemir and K. Guven, *Arch. Pharm.*, 2005, **338**, 96.
13. F. F. Barsoum, H. M. Hosni and A. S. Girgis, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **14**, 3929.
14. A. Gursoy, S. Demirayak, G. Capan and K. Vural, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 359.
15. M. Abid and A. Azam, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **40**, 935.
16. P. Y. Rajendra, R. A. Lakshmana, L. Prasoon, K. Murali and K. P. Ravi, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **15**, 5030.
17. E. Aeillo, S. Aeillo, F. Mingoia, A. Bacchi, G. Pelizzi, C. Musiu, M. Setzu, A. Pani and M. Marongiu, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **8**, 2719.
18. W. Schwabe and J. L. Willmore, *Curr. Op. Invest. Drug*, 2001, **2**, 1763.
19. L. A. Sorbera, P. A. Leeson and J. A. Castaer, *Drug Fut.*, 2000, **25**, 1145.
20. G. Gupta, R. K. Jain, J. P. Maikhuri, P. K. Shukla, M. Kumar, A. K. Roy, V. Singh and S. Batra, *Human Reproduction*, 2005, **20**, 2301.
21. B. J. Berger, *Antimicrob Agent Chemo.*, 2004, **44**, 2540.
22. I. O. Edafiogho, K. R. Scott, J. A. Moore and U. A. Farrar, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **4**, 387.
23. J. Ure and M. J. Perassolo, *Neurological Science*, 2000, **1**, 177.
24. R. Sharma, D. P. Nagda and G. L. Talesara, *ARKIVOC*, 2006, **i**, 1.
25. N. Dixit, D. P. Nagda, S. Ojha and G. L. Talesara, *Afnidad*, 2006, **63**, 223.
26. T. Banu, S. Rajora, D. Khatri and G. L. Talesara, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 300.
27. B. Singh, D. Mehta, L. K. Baregama and G. L. Talesara, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 1306.
28. W. R. Ondroff and S. D. Pratt, *Am. Chem. J.*, 1917, **47**, 89.
29. A. Simmons, "Practical Medical Microbiology", 14th ed., Churchill Livingstone, Edinberg, 1996, **11**, 163.
30. P. S. Bisen and K. Verma, "Hand Book of Microbiology", 1st ed., CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 1996.